

Zones of Depletion

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1. *Common Exhaustion*. Depletion is more than a term, it offers a way to map a terrain, to delineate a horizon from within which to articulate a politics of depletion. Traversing an open semantic field to sketch a cartography of the political, the use of depletion as a shifting vantage point to survey sites and situations of physical and psychosocial exhaustion opens up new modes of relation, suggesting that we translate shared (semantic) properties into technologies of the common as we connect the exhaustion of resources to the depression that follows the work of the soul and the cellularization of the work day. Depletion is where the common begins, in sites to which no-one lays claims because they have been exhausted. Exhaustion leaves fragments, ruins, waste, its ethico-political economies emerge after production, after use, after work. Tracking the abandonment of technologies rather than economies of abundance, depletion shares sensibilities with steampunk, survivalism, and subterranean materialisms of the encounter. Developing at the edge of statist imaginaries, depletion is here to stay¹.

2. *Craft Takes Command*. The small-scale artisan economies special to maker cultures illustrate the difficulty of matching the neoindustrial imagination of making with the scale-free mesh of molecular matters. At worst, such practices 'integrate the point of view of manual labour back into a sociomorphism derived entirely from nonmanual understandings of labour activity'². Initiated in the context of a global venture capital scene, maker networks call attention to the becoming-machinic of craft under the conditions of algorithmic capitalism³. But we can articulate this return of gesture beyond a contemplative materialism, including the 'forgotten space' of global supply chains, the recursive indexicality of financial markets, and the lifestream logistics sustaining the user-as-product paradigms that have turned aesthetic experience into a metamodel of commercial innovation⁴. We can use it, that is, to engage the enclosure of experience.

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1 On matters of exhaustion, also see Carolin Wiedemann and Soenke Zehle (eds), *Depletion Design: A Glossary of Network Ecologies*, Amsterdam: Institute of Network Cultures, 2012, <http://dd.xmlab.org>

2 See McKenzie Wark, 'A More Lovingly Made World', *Cultural Studies Review* 19.1 (2013): 302. Available at: <http://epress.lib.uts.edu.au/journals/index.php/csrj/index>

3 See Chris Anderson, *Makers: The New Industrial Revolution*, New York: Crown Business, 2012; Richard Sennett, *The Craftsman*, Yale: Yale University Press, 2008.

4 See Allan Sekula and Noël Burch, 'The Forgotten Space: Notes for a Film', *New Left Review* 69 (May-June 2011), <http://newleftreview.org/11/69/allan-sekula-noel-burch-the-forgotten-space>.

3. *Electric Dreams*. The current shift toward cloud-based computing, we are told, will turn computing into something like electricity, a utility, possibly a future public good⁵. And if software is the steam engine of our time, what we might learn from steampunk is what it means to dwell on the threshold of an electrical age, of using one technology as the reflexive boundary of another. A term created in 1987 by K. W. Jeter to describe the alternate-history, retro-technology works written by Tim Powers, James Blaylock, and himself (Jeter was a close friend of Philipp K. Dick's and author of three sequels to *Do Androids Dream of Electric Sheep?*), steampunk has evolved into a stable register of global maker networks, rooted in an ethos of design and creativity which acknowledges the humanly physical, that which we can understand with our fingers⁶. Whenever it reaches beyond rummaging the global wasteyards of our electric dreams for prototypes of the neoanalogue, steampunk shifts the focus of collaborative creation from the newness of objects to the ruins of use. Its comprehension of the death of objects (of a certain kind of objecthood) is not about the past but 'the instability and obsolescence of our own times', reminding us that 'the way that we live has already died.'⁷ And even steampunk's irritating imperial nostalgia, rekindled in neo-Victorian imaginaries of a global concatenation of diy practices, contains a sober reminder of the centrality of oikopolitics to the reproduction of economic and social order in times of financialization.

4. *Pragmatist Pathos*. The return of the undead as exhausted subjects no longer capable of maintaining a social order mirrors our own exhaustion, prompting survivalist strategies as if self-organization, muted by the inscription of selves into the matrices of competitive self-optimization, can only be accessed as an instinct triggered by the fear of contagion⁸. In *The Walking Dead*, the everyday of life within a plague of apocalyptic proportions is not marked by a search for origins of crisis but the creation of structures of self-defence out of the ruins of our economic, political and social institutions. Yet the self-transcendence in the face of adversity that is the core of every ethos of self-empowerment (writ large in the current superheroism renaissance powered by comics conglomerates) appears as the sobering reordering of modes of relation, the patriarchal pathos of a violent pragmatism exploring the usefulness of remaining models of reference by assessing their capacity to meet the immediate demands of the state of exception rather than assist passages beyond survival toward a horizon of liberation: the alternative thought experiment of an order created out of contagion that does not fold contact back into contract.⁹

5. *Swerving Matter*. Whereas idealist teleologies may have found refuge in the evangelisms emanating from the former Valley of Heart's Delight, contractual thought does not survive in aleatory materialisms: in the Lucretian narrative of contagion genealogical ties only serve to tragically multiply the corpses ... there is no demand for austerity, no dream of re-foundation¹⁰. The latter offer us an a-topian thought of autonomy unrelated either to the house-

5 Nicholas Carr, *The Big Switch: Rewiring the World, from Edison to Google*, New York: W. W. Norton & Company, 2008.

6 Nick Harkaway, 'The Steampunk Movement is Good and Important', (17/03/2013), <http://harkaway.tumblr.com/post/45604944287/the-steampunk-movement-is-good-and-important>

7 Bruce Sterling, 'The User's Guide to Steampunk', *Steampunk Magazine* #5 (2008), 30-34, 33.

8 See <http://www.thewalkingdead.com/comics/the-story>.

9 Angela Mitropoulos, 'From precariousness to risk management and beyond', *ecipcp.net* (2011), <http://ecipcp.net/transversal/0811/mitropoulos/en>

10 Angela Mitropoulos, *Contract and Contagion: From Biopolitics to Oikonomia*, Wivenhoe: Minor Compositions:

hold economics that support the financialization of everything or the aesthetic economies of competitive self-optimization. Instead, the swerving matter of the accidental encounter recalls, the always-present circumstance of a transitional phase in which things neither had to transpire as they did and could always turn out to be otherwise than anticipated.¹¹ And a politics of swerving matter does not suggest a retreat from a translocal horizon, quite the contrary, 'there is no local that is not already global as far as the molecules are concerned'¹². We will have to comprehend (and appreciate) anew the scale of the accidental encounter.

6. *Automating Affect*. In Spike Jonze's *Her*, artificial intelligence is above all affective intelligence, the fantasy of an automation of affective labor. From the machine, not from each other, do we learn what it is to be human, what it means to like, to share, to decide, a sobering reminder that the self is possibly just one object among others, its assumed complexity of personhood dwarfed by the power and plasticity of machinic intelligence. Does it come as a surprise that we embrace machines that offer to make the work of the self more efficient, rewarding our faith in the (capitalist) promise of linking gains in the efficiency of the labor process to higher (social) wages with the allure of the algorithmic object, prompting us to follow its protocols of self-constitution? As we long to limit the work of unfolding a self across the algorithmically designed topologies of life and labor, we have already come to love the social media machine, touching its mobile interfaces as if to nurture the cognitive and emotional development of what has already grown into one of our most significant others. And finally, the love affair between a lone user and his polyamorous operating system (whose operation assumes that the extractive economies based on the capture of experience have in fact become scale-free) offers us an image of a 'soft' corporate state, gently nudging us toward decision in the name of our own humanity¹³. If this delineate a dystopian horizon, we should instead map the sites of disappearance in the economies of loss¹⁴.

7. *Traverse Networks*. Once upon a time, the Cartographers Guilds struck a Map of the Empire whose size was that of the Empire, and which coincided point for point with it¹⁵. Temporarily considered a useless venture, the map of empire is now so vast that we welcome misalignments as reminders both of the craft of code and a 'soft thought' that acknowledges that algorithms themselves tend towards abstraction, infinity, or the reality of the incomputable.¹⁶ While repetitive references to server farms as the engine rooms of the digital economy end up affirming the already widespread sense of the seemingly incomprehensible complexity of its algorithmic operations, the invisibility of infrastructures, is only one and at the extreme edge of a range of visibilities¹⁷. The glitch may no longer offer orientation for an antagonistic

2012, 10, 9.

11 Ibid., 20.

12 Benjamin Bratton, 'Notes on Chemistry and Urbanism', *Fulcrum* #84: Transcendence, Architecture Association of London (10/02/2014), <http://fulcrum.aaschool.ac.uk/84>

13 The market for paternalism: Nudge unit leaves kludge unit', *The Economist* (07/02/2014), <http://www.economist.com/blogs/freeexchange/2014/02/market-paternalism>

14 Cesare Casarino, 'Universalism of the Common', *diacritics* 39.4 (2009): 162-176,

15 Jorge Luis Borges, 'On Exactitude in Science', in: *Collected Fictions of Jorge Luis Borges*, trans. Andrew Hurley, London: Allen Lane / Penguin Press, 1998, 704-5, 705. On Google Earth, see Clement Valla, 'The Universal Texture', *Rhizome* (31/07/2012), <http://rhizome.org/editorial/2012/jul/31/universal-texture>.

16 Luciana Parisi and Stamatia Portanova, 'Soft Thought (In Architecture and Choreography)', *Computational Culture* 1 (2011), <http://computationalculture.net/article/soft-thought>

17 Brian Larkin, 'The Politics and Poetics of Infrastructure', *Annual Review of Anthropology* 42 (2013), 327-43,

politics, but it helps map the sites through which the enclosure of experience proceeds.

7. *Scaling Sense*. Whether in the name of a search for an infancy of experience or the poesis of collaborative constitution, we continue to make the common of experience the source of retreat and renewal. Sense is at the core of experience. As we follow (and allow) the folding of the algorithmic into experience, we witness the end of objecthood as we know it; not as the autonomy of 'smart' objects but as the dispersal of the technical object into the processuality of networks¹⁸. Maybe we can learn from the dispersal of the algorithmic machine how to figure (give a body to) a political subject whose autonomy is rooted neither exclusively in its status as (liberal) bearer of rights nor in an ownership of the self based on the comprehension of the gestures of self-constitution as work. As each body is already multiple, a gestural ensemble whose provisional unity is provided by deliberately choreographed narratives and the ongoing work of the self increasingly structured by algorithmic prompts from across our own networks, so the idea of collective existence is no longer an alien aggregate, it is part of what we already are. (However, if the elaboration of common futures were a more widely shared desire we would not continue to struggle with the absence of solidarity.) Rereading the late Stuart Hall affirmation of a 'will to connect', there is a sense of the need to explore the making of networks as element of procedural literacies that only the act of making contains and communicates: gesture is what the body does to itself¹⁹. Above and beyond yet another injunction to enlarge the space of the self, the making of networks scales our senses, and we'll soon have to figure out what to do with these sensibilities. Maybe we'll start by experiencing a heightened sense of the local, identifying the registers of the global that constitute its economic, cultural, and social architecture. The extent of our connectedness is overwhelming, but that should not be what exhaust us.

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18 Erich Hoerl, 'The Artificial Intelligence of Sense: The History of Sense and Technology after Jean-Luc Nancy (by way of Gilbert Simondon)', trans. Arne De Boever, *Parrhesia* 17 (2013): 11-24, http://www.parrhesiajournal.org/parrhesia17/parrhesia17_horl.pdf.

19 Stuart Hall, 'Cultural Studies and its Theoretical Legacies', in Lawrence Grossberg et al. (eds), *Cultural Studies*, London: Routledge 1992, 277-85, 278.